

The Mausoleum of Sunan Muria, Colo (Central Java)

also known as "Makam Sunan Muria, Colo (Jawa Tengah)"

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Southeast Asian Religions, Religious Place, Sufi, Mausoleum

Sunan Muria (d. ~ 1551 AD)—also known as Raden Umar Said—belongs to the younger generation of Wali Songo that include Sunan Kudus. The Wali Songo refers to the nine main saints who introduced Islam on the island of Java between the fifteenth and the sixteenth centuries. Historians lack definitive details of Sunan Muria's life as legends blot out what is factually knowable of him. There are two divergent accounts of Sunan Muria's genealogy. In the first account, the saint is portrayed as the son of Sunan Kalijaga who married Dewi Sujinah, the daughter of Sunan Ngudung (the imam of the Grand Mosque at Demak) and the sister of Sunan Kudus. In the second account, entitled *Pustoko Darah Agung*, Sunan Muria is the son of Sunan Ngudung and the nephew of Sunan Kalijaga (R. Darmowasito). Nevertheless, it is plausible that Sunan Muria was the son of Sunan Kalijaga as one of his sons earned the appellation of Sunan Adilangu, a title traditionally bestowed by the Sultan of Demak on the descendants of Sunan Kalijaga. Sunan Muria's dakwah (act of inviting people to embrace Islam) strategy was firmly situated in the everyday lives of the Javanese. In his dakwah, the saint used wayang kulit (a Javanese puppet shadow play) and enacted themes from the Hindu epic Mahabharata but the characters conveyed Islamic themes. Sunan Muria invested the Hindu ritual of shradha (ceremonies performed in honor of deceased ancestors) with a new Islamic meaning. The pre-Islamic Javanese tradition of offering rice cones to one's ancestors was replaced with slametan (feast) and Islamic prayers. Apart from incorporating pre-Islamic elements in his dakwah, Sunan Muria also deployed the Javanese practice of tapa ngeli (drifting in the river by self-isolation) such that the radiance of divine light could enter the conscience. Tapa ngeli was a kind of ascetic self-control. Sunan Muria has bequeathed Javanese Islam its distinct cultural form. The mausoleum complex of Sunan Muria—located in Colo village on Mount Muria, a dormant volcano—reflects distinctive elements of Javanese architecture including a wooden cupola of the Sunan Muria mosque. The cupola consists of two overlapping roofs capped by a mustoko or memolo roof finial. The mustoko—although associated with Brahmamula containers of the essence of divine unity in Hindu cosmogony—makes its appearance in most Javanese mosques during the sixteenth century.

Date Range: 1551 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Central Java, Indonesia

Region tags: Southeast Asia, Indonesia, Java

The shaded region on the map includes the tomb of Sunan Muria, located in Colo village, on the slopes of Mount Muria in the Kudus district of Central Java in Indonesia.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: James Fox, "Interpreting the Historical Significance of Tombs and Chronicles in Contemporary Java," in *The Potent Dead: Ancestors, Saints and Heroes in Contemporary Indonesia*, Henry Chambert-Loir and Anthony Reid edited (Honolulu: ASAA and University of Hawaii Press, 2002).
- Source 2: George Quinn, *Bandit Saints of Java: How Java's Eccentric Saints are Challenging Fundamentalist Islam in Modern Indonesia* (Burrough-on-the-Hill, Leices.: Monsoon Books, 2019).
- Source 3: Ahmad Falah, "Spiritualitas Muria: Akomodasi Tradisi dan Wisata," *Walisongo* 20, no. 2 (2012): 429-53.
- Source 1: Claude Guillot et Henri Chambert-Loir, "Pelirinage sur la tombs de Sunan Muria (Colo, Java Central)," *Archipel* 45 (1993): 97-110.
- Source 2: Claude Guillot dan Henri Chambert-Loir, "Indonesia," in *Ziarah dan Wali di Dunia Islam*, Henri

Chambert-Loir and Claude Guillot edited (Jakarta and Paris: Serambi and Ecole Francaise d' Extreme Oriental, 2007), 333-61.

– Source 1: Agus Sunyoto, *Atlas Wali Songo: Buku Pertama Yang Mengungkap Wali Songo Sebagai Fakta Sejarah* (Bandung: Pustaka IIMaN dan Lesbumi, 2017).

– Source 2: Umar Hasyim, *Sunan Muria Antara Fakta dan Legenda* (Kudus: Menara Kudus, 1983).

– Source 3: Solichin Salim, *Sekitar Wali Sanga* (Kudus: Menara Kudus, 1960).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.delpher.nl/nl/kranten/view?query=soenan+moeria&coll=ddd&page=2&identifier=MMKB23:001761058:mpeg21:a00032&resultsidentifier=MMKB23:001761058:mpeg21:a00032>

– Source 1 Description: H. Kadiman, " Het Graf van Soenan Moeria, " *De Locomotief*, February 1, 1935 [Dutch newspaper].

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.delpher.nl/nl/kranten/view?query=soenan+moeria&page=2&coll=ddd&identifier=MMKB23:001754109:mpeg21:a00105&resultsidentifier=MMKB23:001754109:mpeg21:a00105>

– Source 2 Description: " Een Vacantieoord op de Moeria Helling, " *De Locomotief*, June 21, 1935.

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.delpher.nl/nl/kranten/view?query=soenan+moeria&page=1&coll=ddd&identifier=ddd:010286079:mpeg21:a0202&resultsidentifier=ddd:010286079:mpeg21:a0202>

– Source 3 Description: " Legende van Soenan Moeria, " *De Indische Courant*, July 15, 1938.

Notes: Delpher is a Dutch database that provides digital copies of historical newspapers. 1. H. Kadiman's article highlights the location of the mausoleum of Sunan Muria in Colo village. The tomb of Sunan Muria, notes the article, is situated thirty minutes from Colo village. Furthermore, the article establishes a genealogical link between the families of Sunan Muria and Sunan Kudus, respectively. 2) A richly descriptive article on the pilgrimage to the mausoleum of Sunan Muria. 3) Description of the Mausoleum of Sunan Muria. Pilgrims throng the shrine on Hari Kamis Legi (Thursday that coincides with the five-week cycle of the Javanese calendar). Even during the 1930s, the shrine was visited by the Javanese, Chinese and Europeans. Pilgrims seek the holy water in the mausoleum that is stored in a gentong (Javanese: large earthen pot, a relic from Sunan Muria's time). The water is believed to possess healing properties. The article expatiates on Sunan Muria's legend related to the Sacred Door at Muktihardjo village. According to the oral tradition, after visiting his brother Sunan Bonang, Sunan Muria was returning to the slopes of Mount Muria. On the way, as Sunan Muria was struggling to cross a river in spate, he was assisted by a female carabao (Javanese: kebo, Malay: kerbau). As a mark of gratitude, Sunan Muria offered holy water to the carabao. Miraculously, the carabao gave birth to a boy, Sunan Muria named the child Bambang Bonjabrang. Sunan Muria built a house for Bambang Bonjabrang at Muktihardjo village but the saint stipulated that Bambang Bonjabrang source the door to his house from the Majapahit palace. Although Bambang Bonjabrang managed to secure the Majapahit palace door, Brawijaya (the reigning Majapahit monarch) put up a tough fight. Sunan Muria had to broker peace, placed the door at Bambang Bonjabrang's house at Muktihardjo village and returned to his abode at Mount Muria. Although the credibility of the legend can be challenged, the story nevertheless highlights how Sunan Muria had to negotiate between adat (customary law) and Islam.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The grave of Syekh Sadzali was unearthed in 1920 in Japan village on the slopes of Mount Muria, not far from the mausoleum of Sunan Muria. Bricks inscribed with the year 1267 unearthed. This shows that Islam in Java predates the arrival of the Wali Songo.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: ~ 1920 AD

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Field doesn't know.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Mountain

– Other [specify]: Mount Muria is a domant volcano.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Terracing

– Other [specify]: 1000 steps on the slope of Mount Muria lead to the mausoleum complex.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Other [specify]: Terraced stairs on the slopes of Mount Muria lead to the mausoleum.

A group of structures:

– Yes

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No
- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes
- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

 - Worship
 - Notes: To seek the saint's intercession on their behalf.
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Communal
- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes
- ↳ In antiquity
 - More than once
- ↳ In modernity
 - Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

- Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: To saint Sunan Muria.
- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The death of Sunan Muria

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Field doesn't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Brick walls support the cupola of the mosque and the tomb of Sunan Muria. Ceramic plates used to decorate the wall of the mirhab (niche in the wall containing the kiblat, direction to the Ka'aba). Stairways to the mausoleum built of concrete.

–Yes [specify]: Cupola of tomb sculpted out of limestone. At the entrance to the mosque, the visitor is greeted by a majestic bedug (Javanese drum).

Reference: Guillot, Claude, and Henri Loir. "Pelerinage Sur La Tombe De Sunan Muria". Archipel 45, no. 1 (January 1, 1993). https://www.persee.fr/doc/arch_0044-8613_1993_num_45_1_2896. p.97-110

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Naga or dragon (carved of wood) grace the drum hanger.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Lotus motif at the base of the four soko guru (wooden pillar) with reference to Sunan Muria mosque. The motif is cast out of stone. The tomb of Sunan Muria is situated in a walled chamber within the mausoleum complex that contains 16 other tombs belonging to the family of Sunan Muria. Sunan Muria's grave is protected by a cupola cast out of limestone. Furthermore, the saint's tomb is protected with a wooden door. It is important to note that the mausoleum can be reached from the mosque by descending concrete stairways. Sunan Muria's tomb's wooden door reflects elaborate ornamentation (floral motifs and trellises).

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Calligraphy in Arabic right above the mirhab of the mosque containing an istighotsah (supplication to Allah).

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The grave of Sunan Muria is marked by its simplicity.

Notes: The grave of Sunan Muria is marked by its simplicity. Tombstone of the Demak type. No ornamentation evident on the tombstone.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: A relief depicting two nagas (dragons) with heads turning away from each other gracing the drum hanger. Above the mythical nagas, are four birds.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: Calligraphy in Arabic right above the mirhab of the mosque containing an istighotsah (supplication to Allah).
–Other [specify]: Behind drum's wooden hanger, an Arabic inscription. In front of the drum hanger, inscription with Javanese letters and roman numerals.

↳ Other type of decoration:
–Yes [specify]: The tomb of Sunan Muria is protected by a wooden door. The walls of the tomb are built of limestone, panels reflect ornamentation. Carvings are evident on the gate to the tomb of Sunan Muria as well as its wooden door.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
– Yes

↳ Humans
– No

↳ Supernatural narratives
– No

↳ Human narratives
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No
Notes: Commemoration of the dead.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:
– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:
Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.
– No

Are grave goods present:
– No

Are formal burials present:
– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– No

↳ In cemetery:
– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:
– Yes

- ↳ Domestic context:
Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
– No
- ↳ Other
–Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

- ↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes
- ↳ Are they sky deity:
– No
- ↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No
- ↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No
- ↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No
- ↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No
- ↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No
- ↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes
- ↳ Are they other:
–Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes
- ↳ In dreams:
– Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

Notes: The juru kunci or the key-keeper of the shrine intercedes on behalf of the pilgrims.

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Field does not know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Libations:
 - No
 - ↳ Offerings of food:
 - Yes [specify]: Nasi pincuk served on the 15th of the Islamic month of Muharram, the day Sunan Muria died.
 - Reference: Auliya, Yudha. "salin Luwur Dan Haul Sunan Muria Besok Digelar Tertutup, Nasi Pincuk Dibagikan Door to Door". Muria News, n.d.. <https://www.murianews.com/2020/09/02/194634/salin-luwur-dan-haul-sunan-muria-besok-digelar-tertutup-nasi-pincuk-dibagikan-door-to-door>.
 - ↳ Animal sacrifice:
 - Yes [specify]: Buffalos slaughtered for slametan (feast) sponsored by pilgrims as a gesture of thanksgiving to the saint.
 - ↳ Human sacrifice:
 - No
 - ↳ Sacred objects:
 - No
 - ↳ Daily life objects:
 - Yes [specify]: Donations of small denominations of Indonesian rupiah.
 - ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: Field does not know.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
 - Yes
 - Notes: A nadhar contract is one in which a pilgrim makes a vow to do something such as holding a slametan feast that is conditional upon answering of prayers.
 - Reference: Quinn, George. *Bandit Saints of Java: How Java's Eccentric Saints Are Challenging Fundamentalist Islam in Modern Indonesia*. Burrough on the Hill, Leicester: Monsoon Books,

2019. https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Bandit_Saints_of_Java/UYCFDwAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=bandit+saints+of+java+date+of+publication&printsec=frontcover.

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: The veneration of pre-Islamic sacred places were transformed into mausoleums of Sufi saints with the advent of Islam in the Indonesian archipelago.

Notes: It is believed that the Islamic saint sits on God's side after experiencing death. The cult of saints provided an accessible bridge between different spiritual concepts of Islam and Javanese traditions.

Reference: Chambert-Loir, Henri, and Anthony Reid. "Introduction". In *The Potent Dead: Ancestors, Saints and Heroes in Contemporary Indonesia*. Asian Studies of Australia in Association with Allen & Unwin and University of Hawaii Press, 2002.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Animals are sacrificed on Idul Adha.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Small denominations of Indonesian rupaiah placed by pilgrims in the donation box to secure the ngalap berkah or favor of the saint (Quinn 2019).

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Small denominations of Indonesian rupiah.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Flowers are offered at the grave of Sunan Muria.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Imam of Masjid Sunan Muria; by the juru kunci (key keeper of the tomb)

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The shrine has been frequently renovated. Of the seventeen tombs in Sunan Muria's mausoleum, the ledger of 1 tomb is damaged. The stairways between Masjid Sunan Muria and the mausoleum are in a poor condition and turn slippery during the rains.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Historians are uncertain with respect to the precise date the mausoleum of Sunan Muria was constructed. Nevertheless, it is apparent that the original mosque was built of wood and was recently renovated in 2014. During Sunan Muria's time, the saint had constructed a prayer house (mushola). The mushola was subsequently redeveloped into a mosque.

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– Yes

↳ Transition to adulthood

– Yes

Notes: Circumcision ceremonies for pre-adolescent children are performed in the shrine.

↳ Death

– Yes

Notes: Prayers for deceased ancestors are offered at the tomb of Sunan Muria immediately before the onset of the Holy Month of Ramadhan.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pilgrims undertake ziarah (tomb visitation) to satisfy personal interests including career advancement such as clearing the highly-competitive Indonesian Civil Service Examination (PNS or Pegawai Negeri Sipil).

– Other [specify]: Many married couples undertake ziarah with the hope for progeny whilst a few individuals undertake ziarah to deepen their knowledge of mystic practices.

– Other [specify]: Specific shrines near Sunan Muria's mausoleum visited. See notes below.

Notes: The grave of Syekh Syadzali, a pupil of Sunan Muria is situated about two miles from the mausoleum of Sunan Muria. Pilgrims undertake ziarah to this grave to find a solution to illness afflicting themselves and their family members. Individuals keen on starting a business or desirous of fixing the marriage of their children or starting a new business, visit the graves of Sunan Gadung Sosrokusumo and Sunan Gading, companions of Sunan Muria for securing ngalap berkah (favor).

Reference: Falah, Ahmad. "Spiritualitas Muria: Akomodasi Tradisi Dan Wisata". *Walisongo* 20, no. 2 (November 23, 2012).
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21580/ws.20.2.207>.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Notes: During Idul Adha, soon after participating in the Grebeg ceremony at Demak to welcome the Haj night of Zulhijah, a tumpeng (yellow sticky rice shaped as a cone) procession, representing the nine Wali Songo takes place between the pendopo (pavilion/in this context town hall) of Demak regency and the tomb of the Sultan of Bintoro in Demak, a place for ziarah. Soon after, pilgrims undertake ziarah to the tomb of Sunan Kalijaga and Sunan Kudus before continuing their journey to the mausoleum of Sunan Muria.

Reference: Mundakir, M.. "Rituals Around the Tomb of the Wali: The Implementation of Islamic Sharia of Demak and Kudus Communities". *Addin* 14, no. 2 (December 1, 2020).
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.21043/addin.v14i2.8201>.

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: (a) During the Lebaran season, seven days after the conclusion of Ramadhan during the month of Syawal, Yayasan Sunan Muria (the private foundation in-charge of the mausoleum and the shrine) organizes a Sewu Kupa parade. It is a cultural tradition in honor of Sunan Muria that has roots in adat or local customs. The kupa are rice cakes wrapped in palm leaves. Kupa that is paraded through the village of Colo is shaped as a cone. The procession finally enters the mausoleum of Sunan Muria. People scramble for a piece of the kupa as the cake is believed to contain the blessing of the saint. Apart from the kupa parade, there is a display of crops grown on the slopes of Mount Muria. The local government is involved in the festivities as well. (b) The 15th of the Islamic month of Muharram is commemorated as the death anniversary of Sunan Muria. On this day, the draped cloth over Sunan Muria's tombstone is ritually changed. At this time, pilgrims chant surah Yasin and surah Tahliil verses from the al-Quran. Istighotsah (Istighosha), a supplication to Allah to free oneself of obstacles is chanted by pilgrims four times. Soon after a feast (slametan) consisting of sacrificial buffalo meat and rice is served to at least 25,000 people.

Reference: Putut, Nugroho Dwi-Putranto. "Parade Sewu Kupa, Tradisi Penghormatan Untuk

Sunan Muria". Kompas, n.d.. <https://travel.kompas.com/read/2018/06/23/154340727/parade-sewu-kupat-tradisi-penghormatan-untuk-sunan-muria?page=all>.

Reference: NU Online. "Kepungan Nasi Berkah Warnai Buka Luwur Sunan Muria". NU Online (Nahdlatul Ulama Online), n.d.. <https://www.nu.or.id/daerah/kepungan-nasi-berkah-warnai-buka-luwur-sunan-muria-PDuo0>.

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Yayasan Sunan Muria, the foundation in-charge of the mausoleum of Sunan Muria.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: A dedicated space in Masjid Muria.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Annual

Notes: 1) The tradition of "Buka Luwur" or the ritual changing of the draped cloth covering Sunan Muria's tombstone is observed on the 15th of the Islamic month of Muharram, coinciding with the saint's death anniversary although historians lack definitive details of the chronology of the saint's life. The ceremonies stretch over a two-week period, commencing from the Islamic New Year (observed on the 1st of Muharram). At the same time, springs in the vicinity of the tomb complex are cleaned. On the 1st of Muharram, pilgrims silently recite select verses from the al-Quran. Yayasan Sunan Muria also mobilizes pilgrims to donate to orphans on the 10th of Muharram (Asyura). As the draped cloth is ceremonially changed on the 15th of Muharram (nighttime), pilgrims recite surah Yasin and surah Tahliil verses from the al-Quran. Istighotsah (Istighosha), a supplication to Allah to free oneself of obstacles is chanted by pilgrims four times. Soon after the mandatory prayers, pilgrims partake nasi bungkus (rice wrapped in teak leaves) and meat from buffalos specially sacrificed for the occasion. The feast (Javanese: slametan) on the 15th of Muharram night is organized by Yayasan Sunan Muria and at least 25,000 pilgrims congregate at the tomb of Sunan Muria in connection with the Buka Luwur ritual. It is believed that feasting at the shrine earns the ngalap berkah (favours) from the saint. 2) Tradisi Sewu Kupat or The Ketupat food festival, that coincides with the seventh day of Lebaran. 3) Towards the close of Islamic month of Rajab (preceding Ramadhan), the shrine draws Javanese who pay homage to their deceased ancestors at the shrine. 4) Mawlid (birthday of Prophet Muhammad). 5) The ceremonial bathing of Sunan Muria's saddle is known as "Guyang Cekathak," in the Javanese language. The ritual bathing of the saddle that belonged to Sunan Muria's horse takes place on Wage Jumat (Friday that corresponds to the Javanese five-day week centered on the pasar or market). The festival falls sometime in the month of September at the peak of the dry season across Java. Sunan Muria's saddle is paraded from Masjid Sunan Muria to the Sendang Rejoso spring. The parade is accompanied by the tune of the tambourine and the chanting of the Prophet's Prayer. Soon after Sunan Muria's horse saddle is ceremonially bathed in the waters of Sendang Rejoso, the spring water is ceremonially sprinkled on participants. After the washing of the horse saddle, participants recite a prayer for rain. A feast consisting of opor ayam (chicken cooked in coconut milk), vegetables, mutton is then served to participants.

The Guyang Cekathak ritual is a procession invoking Allah to shower abundant rains. Days particularly propitious for undertaking ziarah to the mausoleum of Sunan Muria include Rebo-Kliwon (Wednesday that coincides with the five-day week of the Javanese calendar in a 35-day cycle), Legi Kamis (Thursday) that coincides with the five-day week of the Javanese calendar in a 35-day cycle, and Pahing Jumat or Friday that coincides with the five-day week of the Javanese calendar in a 35-day cycle.

Reference: Sari, Sekar. "Suronan Dan Tradisi Buka Luwur Di Beberapa Daerah Jawa Tengah". *Harian Muria*, n.d.. <https://harianmuria.com/kajian/suronan-dan-tradisi-buka-luwur-di-beberapa-daerah-jawa-tengah/>.

Reference: AYO SURABAYA.COM. "Mengenal Sunan Muria Dan Guyang Cekathak, Ritual Pemanggil Hujan Untuk Melestarikan Sendang Rejoso". AYO SURABAYA.COM, n.d.. <https://www.ayosurabaya.com/hot-news/pr-782188688/mengenal-sunan-muria-dan-guyang-cekathak-ritual-pemanggil-hujan-untuk-melestarikan-sendang-rejoso?page=2>.

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- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members
- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No
- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: at least 25,000 during the slametan held in conjunction with the Buka Luwur rituals on the 15th day of Muharram.
- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Elites
 - Non-elites
 - Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- Yes

- ↳ Incubation
 - No

- ↳ Healing magic
 - Yes

- ↳ Cleansing
 - Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Spring with Three Flavors (Air Mata Tiga Rasa)

Notes: In the village of Japan, not far from Sunan Muria's mausoleum and near the grave of ulama Syekh Hasan Sadzali, a spring famously known as Air Mata Tiga Rasa or a Spring with Three Flavors is situated. Syekh Sadzali was an ulema (Muslim scholars well-versed in sharia and theology) from the Middle East and his life predates that of Sunan Muria. He wanted to secure uzlah (retreat) to get closer to God. He chose the slopes of Mount Muria for his dakwah. At the time (c. 13th century), Mount Muria was situated on an island in the Java sea (but today the island, on which Mount Muria was situated, is a part of the island of Java due to tectonic changes induced by volcanic eruptions). Bricks inscribed with the year 1267 AD have been discovered from the site. Additionally, ceramic bowls, believed to date back to Syekh Sadzali's time have been unearthed from the site. A well relic [well of life] dating back to Syekh Sadzali's times have been discovered near the grave of Syekh Sadzali. The well was built of curved bricks. According to a local legend, Syekh Sadzali was worried that people may drown in the well, he sealed it. Subsequently, a spring "Air Mata Tiga Rasa" or a Spring with Three Flavors appeared at the site of the well. The waters from the Spring with Three Flavors is much sought by pilgrims due to its therapeutic properties and is believed to contain the berkah (favor or grace) of Syekh Hasan Sadzali. The three flavors indicate treatment of disease, increasing a person's self-confidence, and sustenance. The three tastes apparent in the Spring with three flavors: tasteless, spirit-like and wine-like. Pilgrims undertaking ziarah to the mausoleum of Sunan Muria also visit the Spring with Three Flavors.

Reference: Auliya, Yuda Rahman. "Syekh Hasan Sadzali Rejenu Kudus, Penyebar Islam Kaya Raya Yang Menyepi Di Muria". *Muria News*, n.d.
<https://www.murianews.com/2022/08/23/310500/syekh-hasan-sadzali-rejenu-kudus-penyebar-islam-kaya-raya-yang-menyepi-di-muria>.

– Other [specify]: See also the Myth of Parijoto (night-flowering jasmine)

Notes: The parijoto plant is native to South and Southeast Asia and has considerable medicinal value. As such, it is sought by practitioners of traditional medicine across South and Southeast Asia. According to a local legend in the vicinity of Mount Muria, during her seventh month of pregnancy, Sunan Muria's wife consumed the seeds of the plant and subsequently gave birth to a healthy child. Pilgrims believe that Sunan Muria intercedes to Allah on behalf of those childless couples who are desirous of progeny. Parijoto plants are endemic to Mount Muria and the seed is sold widely near the mausoleum of Sunan Muria. Sinom Parijoto was the name of a Javanese song, used extensively by Sunan Kalijaga in his dakwah. The song urges individuals to abandon laziness, lust and anger.

Reference: Hanum, Alima Saida, Erma Prihastanti, and Jumari Jumari. "Ethnobotany of Utilization, Role, and Philosophical Meaning of Parijoto (medinilla, Spp) on Mount Muria in Kudus Regency, Central Java". *AIP Conference Proceedings* 1868, no. 1 (August 11, 2017).
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.4995210>.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 25,000

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Annual

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Majelis Ulema Indonesia or the Indonesia Ulema Council responsible for orthodoxy checks.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Applicable to the case of the mausoleum of Sunan Muria. The current juru kunci in charge of the mausoleum Muhammad Shokib Garno Sunarno was inspirational in organizing a culinary fest in Colo village. He is the fourteenth descendant of Sunan Muria and He has also spearheaded the formation of a merchant's association

Reference: Rasyid, Shani. "Kisah Inspirasi Muh Shokib, Sang Penjaga Gunung Muria Yang Dicintai Masyarakat". Merdeka.com, n.d.. <https://www.merdeka.com/jateng/kisah-inspirasi-muh-shokib-sang-penjaga-gunung-muria-yang-dicintai-masyarakat.html>.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Javanese

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Reference: Fox, James. "Interpreting the Historical Significance of Tombs and Chronicles in Contemporary Java". In *The Potent Dead: Ancestors, Saints and Heroes in Contemporary Indonesia*. Asian Studies Association of Australia, Allen and Unwin and University of Hawaii Press, 2002.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: The juru kunci or the key keeper of the tomb establishes an authoritative account of each tomb and all figures associated with it. Most juru kunci are related to the tomb personage where they serve.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Yayasan Sunan Muria and the local village community.

Reference: Ibriza, Umi Syifa. *Pengelolaan Yayasan Masjid Dan Makam Sunan Muria Dalam Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Desa Colo Tahun 2013-14*. Semarang: IAIN Walisongo, 2014.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During the colonial period, the descendants of Sunan Muria, especially the juru kunci lost control of land to the colonial government of the Netherlands Indies. In contemporary Indonesia (1949-present), the Central Java High Court held that the land belongs to the government. But the juru kunci have challenged the ruling of the High Court and have referred to village-level land records to prove hereditary ownership of the land.

Reference: Liputan6. "Ahli Waris Sunan Muria Kontra Pemda Kudus". Liputan6.com, n.d.. <https://www.liputan6.com/news/read/11338/ahli-waris-sunan-muria-kontra-pemda-kudus>.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Yayasan Sunan Muria donates clothes and food to orphans and widows during the Islamic New Year (1st of Muharram).

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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<https://alif.id/read/ttt/hikayat-walisongo-9-dakwah-moderat-sunan-muria-melalui-kesenian-dan-kearifan-lokal-b236935p/>.

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https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Masjid_masjid_bersejarah_di_Indonesia/-NnF9RyAl0IC?hl=en&gbpv=1.

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Reference: Yes [specify]: Cupola of tomb sculpted out of limestone. At the entrance to the mosque, the visitor is greeted by a majestic bedug (Javanese drum)., Guillot, Claude, and Henri Loir. "Pelerinage Sur La Tombe De Sunan Muria". *Archipel* 45, no. 1 (January 1, 1993). https://www.persee.fr/doc/arch_0044-8613_1993_num_45_1_2896. p.97-110

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